

MACHINE LEARNING BASED FALSE ALARMS REDUCTION FOR SMALL INFRARED TARGETS

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ABSTRACT

There are many techniques for feature detection in Small Infrared Images and to minimize false alarm rates up-gradation is a must. This paper gives the idea of machine learning dependent target detection where feature extraction is done using Discrete Wavelet Transformation and feature selection is done using Nature Inspire Algorithm that is Particle Swarm Optimization at the end classification is done using classifier Random Forest with filter-based target detection method. Modified Top- Hat filter is used for the filtered database. DWT is used for extraction of features that breaks a target into small parts termed as wavelets obtained from mother wavelet via shifting and dilation. Before feature selection each feature is analyzed using two different approaches first is intensity distribution and other one is probability density function and from both the observation median, mean, entropy, variance shows the best result because overlapping of probability distribution is least in these four. PSO works on the principle of bird flocking together after calculating gbest and pbest of each feature, Variance, Mode, Kurtosis, Zernike moment, Entropy, Skewness are the highest-ranking feature values these features are used further for the classification purpose. Out of all the classifiers logistic regression and random forest classifiers have shown best results for the false alarm reduction rate. Earlier many wrapper-based feature selection algorithms have been used but PSO and random forest classifiers have combinedly reduced false alarm rate by 7.9 whereas without classifiers the false alarm rate was 30.6. FAR without classifier and with classifier improved by 3.7 factor.

Keywords: Discrete Wavelet Transform, Feature Extraction, Particle Swarm Optimization, Random Forest Classifier

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1. INTRODUCTION

Previously Spatial filters like to mean-based, median-based, morphology-based Top-Hat filters and combinational filters like Max-Median, Max-Mean have been used thoroughly for true target detection in infrared images. These filters are based upon simple statistical features like mean filter uses average or Gaussian mean whereas median filter[16] uses statistical orders. The Top-Hat filter has the concept of dilation and erosion with structural elements. Modified Top-Hat filter is an advanced approach to Top-Hat filters. Mean filter [14] is the easiest technique in terms of execution but sensitivity towards edge clutter makes it imperfect. Morphology [17]based and median filters are non-linear filters having a wide range for detection but complex execution and high false alarm rate make it unfit. Situation based false alarm reduction techniques are also prevalent like TBD (track before detect)[9] used when we have static sensor platform than environmental clutters get reduced before targets. It's enhanced version is DP dynamic programming[19] which can also detect dim targets in the environment and Temporal profiles can be used for slow-moving clouds[27]. The Concept of 3 plot correlation with spatial filters is also used for environmental clutters. CFAR[28] constant false alarm rate detector is a decision-based method that determines the target by thresholding or probing a target region. The target detection performance can be enhanced by machine learning-based classifiers. The classifiers are trained by extracted features that are done using Discrete wavelet transform. DWT gives value as wavelet's coefficients, nine coefficients are extracted by probing small targets using thresholding process with the nearest neighbor based classifier. Particle Swarm Optimization based feature selection is done here which is social behavior based algorithm depends on bird flockings. Before feature extraction Pre-processing is done which includes excessive clutter filtering, Normalization. Dimension reduction is done using Feature projection and Selection. Using Feature extraction we get features for detection and recognition for the true targets. The Behavior of an image is determined by its features. Appropriate features must be extracted to differentiate from irrelevant data and to have correct information about input data. From the raw dataset, a feature vector is prepared by the feature extraction technique[2].

Selected features are used for classification by learning classifiers. First a database of feature vector is prepared by using feature extraction. In this paper, Wrapper based feature selection method is used which Nature Inspire algorithm. Wrapper based method is used when feature vector is small in size.

After the introduction, spatial filtering of the image is done before extraction and statistical analysis of set of nine features which is done by Discrete Wavelet Transform. Section 2 shows the feature selection by using Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm. AUC (area under ROC curve) approach is used for selecting appropriate classifier for classification. Distribution of target and clutter is plotted using probability density function to find which feature is more relevant for classification more overlapping of graphs more inappropriate feature is. One more forward feature selection algorithm is also used in this paper for the comparison purpose that is AUC.

Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) [7] plot is a graphical representation between X axis and Y axis that is rate of detection and false alarm rate. Cumulative density of true detection probability is in Y axis and the X shows cumulative density of false detection probability. Range of AUC is between [0,1]. Section 3 highlights experimental results and also AUC based method is used for finding the best classifiers among five classifiers which are Random Forest, Nearest Neighbor, Decision Tree, Gaussian and Logistic Regression. According to AUC based method Random Forest and logistic regression classifiers show the best AUC value hence these are used for classification purposes. Classifiers with Spatial filtered database shows the better results in terms of reduced false alarm rate in comparison to filtered database and the section 4 highlights conclusion part.

2. METHODOLOGIES

This part highlights three parts that are extraction of features, features selection, and detection of target as basic functional elements for Machine Learning classifiers. Fig.1 shows the Flow diagram for proposed work:

Fig.1. Flow for methodology

Preparation of database is done by using basic target detection algorithm. DWT is used for feature extraction purposes in both phases but in testing phase extraction is done after candidate target region probing. Probing is done by using thresholding with the nearest neighbor classification. The Probed region will be considered target according to SCR value. SCR is obtained by deducting the average of all background pixels from the intensity of maximum target signal divided by background standard deviation. If this value is more than user-defined parameter than this is target otherwise it is not. The Value of K depends on average and the maximum target signal. Deciding value of K is called thresholding [10] and after which nearest neighboring based clustering is also done which is shown in Fig.2.

Fig.2. (a) Filter based detection (b) Nearest neighboring clustering

2.1. Feature Extraction

Feature Extraction is done for classification of true target and false alarms and learning of classifiers is done by selected features. In this paper, DWT is used for extraction of features that breaks a target into small parts termed as wavelets obtained from mother wavelet via shifting and dilation. It gives a time and frequency representation. Two-dimensional DWT results in 4 sub-bands LH (low-high), HH (high-high), LL (low-low), HL (high-low). LH and HL bands have better performance as compared to band LL because the LL band is an approximate component of a target according to the previously done work also Daubechies wavelet gives better result for image processing [20][21]. From HL band following features are extracted which are statistical.

1. *Entropy*: Randomness or disorder stored

$$En = \sum(n \times \log(n)) \quad n = \text{counts of histogram} \quad (1)$$

2. *Target Mean*: Average of pixels in targets.

$$\mathbf{m} = [\mathbf{1}/P \sum_{k=1}^k \mathbf{p}_k] \quad (2)$$

p_k = pixel value, P = Total no. of pixels.

3. *Variance*: Moment with order 2.

$$v = \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - x)^2 / N \right] / \sigma^3 \quad (3)$$

N = Pixel count, σ = Pixel standard deviation, x_i = mean

4. *Standard Deviation (S.D)*:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (I_i - \mu)^2 / N} \quad (4)$$

I_i = Pixels Intensity, μ = average intensity, N = pixel count.

5. *Skewness*: Third-order moment

$$S = \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - x)^4 / N \right] / \sigma^3 \quad (5)$$

N =Pixel count, σ = S.D, x =average intensity.

6. *Kurtosis*: Fourth order moment

$$k = \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - x)^4 / N \right] / \sigma^4 \quad (6)$$

N = Total pixel count, σ =S.D, x =mean

7. *Median*: Pixel value in the centre of target

8. *Mode*: More frequently occurring pixel value.

9. *Zernike's moment*: Z.M is an orthogonal moment that does not vary according to position, rotation, and scale. Zernike's polynomials are used for invariant Zernike moment [12][13].

2.2. Feature Selection

PSO algorithm is a wrapper feature selection algorithm [22]. In 1995 Kennedy and Eberhart [25][26] proposed this idea of social behavior algorithm based on bird flocking or we can say fish schooling etc. In PSO [24], the extracted feature vector is a candidate solution considered as a bird flock called a particle. The algorithm works to get the best solution from its memory. Each particle gets assigned a fitness number and a fitness function optimizes and a velocity factor is also assigned to each particle to direct the movement of particles for the best solution. Each particle fits itself according to its memory and neighborhood position to get the best solution. The initialization of particles is done in a manner in search space that the population of particles is randomly distributed. There are two variables in this algorithm pbest and gbest each time the particle achieved the best value according to coordinates called as pbest value and the total best value is called gbest value the particles achieve every time these best values in each iteration by updating the previous values. Below are the steps followed in the PSO algorithm:

1. Initialize the parameters.
2. Each particle gets a fitness value.
3. If new fitness value is better than pbest than this is next pbest otherwise previous pbest is the best value.
4. Among all particles new gbest is pbest of best particle.
5. Find velocity of every particle.
6. Velocity is used to update the data value of each particle.
7. End the process if the target has reached otherwise Go to step2.

2.3. Classifier

After feature selection process selection of optimal and best classifiers is the next step. For this purpose, we have taken five types of classifiers that are Gaussian, Logistic Regression, K Nearest Neighbor, Random Forest and Decision Tree.

Random Forest: It is a classification algorithm incorporating many decision trees. Uses feature randomness and bagging to train many DT parallelly. It does not need any scaling of features. The feature vector as input is given to each DT and each DT chooses a class. If a class has highest votes than RF selects that class.

Logistic Regression(LR): LR is a supervised classifier that predicts the probability of variables. It is dichotomous that is only two values that are 0 and 1. It predicts the value of prior observation. It shows the best relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

Decision Tree(DT): DT is a learning method that is non-parametric supervised classification. It classifies in the form of a tree. The Tree has leaf and nodes final classification or decision is shown from leaf nodes. It works on both data numerical and categorical.

K-Nearest Neighbour Classifier: It is a supervised classification technique depends upon 'sameness' in the proximity. It checks the closeness of labeled points. Uses geometric distance to find the nearest item.

Gaussian Classifier: It is simple and uses a generative approach to model class posterior and input class distribution.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Database Preparation

All the images have been collected from an open-source which is of long-range and mid-wave range. One set of targets and one for clutter images is prepared from different sources. Modified Top-Hat filter (MTH) based filtering is done in this paper for creating the database to extract feature easily.

Fig.3. Database of clutters and targets

Modified Top-Hat filtering [10] filtering DB which is based on erosion and dilation by using structural elements is in Fig.4[29]. MWTH means white top-hat transformation, MBTH means modified black hat transformation. Improvement of SCR values shows that filtered database is essential for feature extraction purpose.

$$mwth(x, y) = \max(i(x, y) - i \circ s(x, y), t - t) \quad (7)$$

$$mbth(x, y) = \max(i \bullet s(x, y) - i(x, y), t) - t \quad (8)$$

Fig.4(a) Infrared Image without detection and with clutter (b) Infrared image after detection

Fig.5 (signal to clutter ratio) SCR for Fig.4(a) and (b)

3.2. Distribution of features (Clutter and Target)

Intensity Distribution of target and clutter for different extracted features is shown in Fig.6[29] where it shows the simple target and clutter distribution values from each image whereas Fig.7 demonstrates pdf (probability density function) of each target and clutter values. If plots of density functions are overlapping then it shows that extracted feature value is less relevant. From this observation, we can say that median, mean, entropy, variance are the best extracted features[10][15].

(1) The entropy value for different clutters and targets

(2) The average feature values for different clutters and targets

(3) The variance values for different clutters and targets

(4) The standard deviation value for different clutters and targets

(5) The Skewness feature values for different clutters and targets

(6) The kurtosis (higher order moment) value for different clutters and targets

(7) The median feature values for different clutters and targets

(8) The mode feature values for different clutters and targets

(9)The Zernike moment feature values for different clutters and targets

Fig.6. Observation of Intensity of each feature

(1)Probability density function of (entropy)

(2) Probability density function (mean)

(3) Probability density function of (variance)

(4) Probability density function (standard deviation)

(5) Probability density function (skewness)

(6) Probability density function (kurtosis)

(7) Probability density function (median)

(8) Probability density function (mode)

(9) Probability density function (Zernike moment)Z.M

Fig.7 Probability density function(pdf) for each feature

3.3. Feature Selection

The selection of suitable extracted features for the classification of true target and clutter is done using PSO. Fig.8 represents the layman structure of the PSO algorithm after feature extraction from the modified database of images, it becomes important to find a more relevant feature subset. For PSO the number of particles is 9 because total extracted feature vectors are 9. According to the above-mentioned algorithm, the first step is to initialize the parameters hence, the number of iterations for the algorithm is 200 the population size is 50. For the calculation of fitness of each particle, a fitness function is required a mean of total data and the standard deviation is used as fitness or objective function.

Among 9 extracted features 6 extracted features selected as a final feature vector and gbest using mean as the objective function is 6.584 and using standard deviation gbest is 5.167. This is shown in Table1.

Fig.8.PSO algorithm

Table1: Table for selected features using two algorithms

Unreduced or Raw Data	PSO based Feature Selection		AUC based Feature Selection
9 Extracted features [1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9]	Mean of data as the fitness function. [3,7,9,6,1,5] Gbest=6.584	Standard deviation as the fitness function. [9,2,8,7,5,1] Gbest=5.167	Featuresubset2 [3,7,6,1,9,5]

From the above data, we can say that Variance, Mode, Kurtosis, Zernike moment, Entropy, Skewness are the highest-ranking feature values according to mean as the fitness function. For the comparison purpose, one more feature selection technique is used in this paper which is a wrapper forward feature selection technique called (Area Under ROC Curve) AUC as shown in Fig.9. Each feature vector has an AUC value, among the highest AUC value we select a feature vector again to calculate AUC values if new AUC is less than previous highest value then the previous feature vector is best vector otherwise calculate another AUC value for new feature vector. Total 6 feature vector outcome as final feature subset. The AUC curve is generated using the NN classifier for the simplicity and normalization of each feature is done before value generation[23].

Fig.9. Comparison of AUC values of each extracted features

Order of features according to AUC:

(3) > (7) > (6) > (1) > (9) > (5) > (8) > (2) > (4) Base feature vector: top AUC rankers taken as base set 5 features are selected, $F_{base1} = [F3, F7, F6, F1, F9]$, Subset $F_{base2} = [F3, F7, F6, F1, F9, F5]$ is the final subset because AUC value of subset 3 reduced as shown in Fig10 and we add feature in the previous until new value of AUC is not less than the last one. Variance > Median > Kurtosis > Entropy > Zernike Moment > Skewness is the order from this algorithm. Hence, we can conclude that both algorithms showing the same features approximately.

Fig.10. AUC value for different feature subsets

3.4. Evaluation of Classifier

A random sample is generated as a training dataset and testing dataset for the comparison of the best classifier for classification purposes. Modified Top-hat filter with five classifiers is used and the AUC value of each is calculated using the ROC curve. For the evaluation Detection rate (DR) with False alarm rate (FAR) are the parameters. ROC value is shown in Fig.11 for each classifier and from the operating conditions. From the ROC curve, we can conclude that the Random Forest classifier, Decision Tree, Logistic Regression classifier showing the same value approx whereas KNN and Gaussian classifiers are showing lesser value in the operating region. Fig.12 shows the performance of these three classifiers.

Fig 11. Classifiers value in the ROC curve.

(a) Modified TopHat[Black Box]+ Random Forest Classifier[Red Box]

(b) Modified TopHat[Black Box]+Logistic Regression Classifier[Yellow Box]

(c) Modified TopHat[Black Box]+ Decision Tree Classifier[Sky Blue Box]

Fig.12. Spatial Target Detection and Classifiers based classification for the random infrared image.

From Fig.12 we can deduce that these three classifiers can be used for the final classification purpose for small infrared targets. This system we checked on targets and clutters images gathered from the open source about 100 testing images taken with ground truth information. Fig.13b shows the detection with and without classifier Random Forest in one dataset and Fig.13a shows with spatial filter only. The yellow box shown in the figure shows ground truth information and blue box shows detection. Similar work is done for the rest of the dataset. Table 2 represents the result obtained by using classifiers for the total number of testing datasets.

Table 2. Detection with and without a classifier

Values	Detector Only	Detector +Classifier
DR	99.1	98.7
FAR	30.6	7.9

Fig.13. (a) Detection without classifier (b) Detection with classifier

4. CONCLUSION

The small targets embedded in any image appear the same when they are far distant objects. Using a machine learning approach is helpful for the reduction of false alarm rates. DWT based extraction of features is used in the paper because it down scales the images effectively in sub-bands and then in the form of coefficients different parameters are extracted as a feature vector. PSO is a simple yet efficient feature selection technique. Among the classifiers Random Forest, Logistic Regression showed the best result for classification. After applying the classification, we can say that there is a reduction in FAR by a factor of 3.7 and detection rate hindered by 0.4% approx. This idea for FAR reduction will be conducted on synthetic datasets, moving target dataset as well for future evaluations.

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